

Kinetic Studies on Slow Coagulation of Thorium Oxide Sol

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A modified form of Smoluchowski's slow coagulation equation proposed by Ghosh has been verified experimentally for ThO_2 sol. The spectrophotometric technique followed has been developed by Mukherjee. The rate of coagulation of ThO_2 sol has been found to be higher with KNO_3 than with KCl as coagulant. The autocatalytic nature found to be absent with well dialysed sol, gradually appears on addition of co-ions. Appearance of S-shape has been explained from a new point of view. Suitable explanation for the constants α , β (or a and b) in the kinetic equation is yet to be advanced.

Smoluchowski's equation¹ for the rate of coagulation of colloid can be expressed as:

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{t}{T_0}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where n_0 represents the number of particles per ml present initially and Σn represents their number after a time t from the start of coagulation and T_0 is the time in which the number of particles is just halved being given by $T_0 = 3\eta/4kTn_0$, η being the viscosity of the dispersion medium, k , Boltzmann constant and T , the absolute temperature. The above equation has been found to hold good for rapid coagulation only. For the process of slow coagulation, he suggested the following equation in which ϵ represents the percentage of encounters between particles which lead to their aggregation²:

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \epsilon \frac{t}{T_0}} \quad (1a)$$

Therefore, all curves representing coagulation with time, either in the rapid or in the slow zone, should be transformable into each other by a suitable change in the time scale. This conclusion is not borne out by experimental results.

In some cases of slow coagulation Σn ceases to decrease any further after sometime³. According to Ghosh^{2,3}, these facts can be accounted for approximately by assuming that

$$\epsilon = \frac{k}{1 + \alpha t}$$

1. Smoluchowski, *Physikal Z.*, 1916, 17, 557, 597;
—*Z. Physikal Chem.* 1917, 92, 129.
2. Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 671.
3. Ghosh and Gangopadhyay, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 811.
4. Kruyt and Van Arkel, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1920, 39, 656;
—*Kolloid Z.*, 1923 32, 29.
5. Westgren, *Ark. kemi. Mineral Geol*, 1918, 7, m 6.

where k and α are constants, and consequently the slow coagulation equation becomes

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0(1 + \alpha t)}{(1 + \beta t)} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where β and α are constants and $\beta > \alpha$.

Equation (2) has been shown^{2,3} to agree well with the data of Kruyt and Van-Arkel⁴ on selenium sol and Westgren⁵ on gold sol, where the number of aggregates has been counted ultramicroscopically.

As the counting of particles is tedious and time-consuming, Mukherjee⁶ has introduced a spectrophotometric technique, in which the light transmitted through the colloid undergoing slow rate of coagulation is measured with time. For this technique, the equation (2) has been shown² to take the form

$$D_t = D_i \frac{(1 + bt)}{(1 + at)} \quad \dots \quad (2a)$$

where a and b are constants, D_i and D_t being the galvanometer deflections at $t=0$ and at any other time t . The expression (2a) has been verified² from the data of Mukherjee and Mazumder⁶ on As_2S_3 sol.

The above equation (2a) can also be expressed as

$$I_t = I_i \frac{(1 + bt)}{(1 + at)} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where I_i is the intensity of light transmitted through the colloid at $t=0$ and I_t that at time t .

In the present paper we shall subject equations (3) and (2) to experimental test using our data on ThO_2 sol and data of Watillon and co-workers⁸ on selenium sol respectively. The appearance of S-shape (the auto-catalytic nature) in the coagulation curve⁷ has also been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

In their experimental study on coagulation of silver sol, Rai and Ghosh⁹ have measured the turbidity of the system at different intervals with the help of a Klett-Summerson colorimeter. The same technique was adopted by us. A green filter allowing light of wave length around 540 μ to pass was used and the temperature maintained at 25°.

Preparation of the Colloid.— ThO_2 sol was prepared by Müller's method¹⁰ with slight modification. To a 5% solution of $Th(NO_3)_4$ heated to 70°, concentrated ammonia was

6. Mukherjee and Mazumder—*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 794.

7. Dassi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 24, 181.

—*Kolloid. Chem. Beiheft.*, 28, 357 (1928).

8. Watillon *et al.*, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1959, 68, 482.

9. Rai and Ghosh, *Kolloid Z.*, 1957, 154, 146.

10. Müller, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4436.

added dropwise with constant stirring until further addition of ammonia gave a permanent precipitate. It was then dialysed against distilled water for one month after which it was stored in a Jena flask for about another month. The positively charged sol is almost colorless with a bluish tinge and has a $pH = 3.54$. Two samples of the sol were prepared, sample A had a concentration of 2.5% and specific conductance at 25° equal of 1.27×10^{-4} mhos at 25°, whereas sample B had a concentration of 2.03% with a specific conductance of 2.1×10^{-4} mhos.

The data recorded in Table I deal with the verification of equation (2) and those in Tables II and III are meant for the verification of equation (3). The formation of S-shaped curves with sol sample B becomes apparent from Fig. 1 (a, b, c & d corresponding to thorium nitrate concentration 0, 0.4, 0.684 and 1.332 m. moles/litre respectively with a fixed coagulant concentration, viz., $C_{KCl} = 66.6$ mM/litre).

TABLE I

Selenium sol G (Fig. 4)^a. $n_0 = 7.8 \times 10^8$ /ml. Particle diameter = 160 m μ . $C_{KCl} = 4$ mM/litre.

	$\Sigma n \times 10^{-8}$	
	Observed.	Calc. for $\alpha = 8.52 \times 10^{-3}$ $\beta = 3.38 \times 10^{-2}$
0.0 min.	7.80	7.80
11.3	6.18	6.19
15.3	5.67	5.61
25.3	5.03	5.12
27.0	4.90	5.09
58.3	4.01	3.92

TABLE II

Sample A.

	I_t $C_{KCl} = 2.86 \times 10^{-2}$ (M).		I_t $C_{KCl} = 2.50 \times 10^{-2}$ (M).		I_t $C_{KCl} = 2.22 \times 10^{-2}$ (M).	
	Obs.	Calc. $a = 0.01336$ $b = 0.00826$	Obs.	Calc. $b = 2.815 \times 10^{-3}$ $a = 4.435 \times 10^{-3}$	Obs.	Calc. $a = 10.44 \times 10^{-3}$ $b = 9.288 \times 10^{-3}$
	0 min.	99.3	99.3	99.3	99.3	99.3
10	95.0	94.8	97.2	97.7	98.3	98.3
20	91.3	91.3	96.2	96.3	97.4	97.4
30	88.4	88.5	95.0	95.0	..	..
40	85.6	86.1	..	..	96.4	96.1
45	..	..	93.3	93.3	..	..
60	81.7	82.4	92.0	91.7	95.5	95.1
80	79.2	79.7	89.8	89.8	..	..
85	..	..	..	..	94.7	94.1
100	77.6	77.6	88.0	88.1	..	..
115	..	..	..	..	93.3	93.3
130	..	..	..	..	..	..
150	75.9	75.2	86.7	86.7	..	..
160	..	..	84.9	84.8	92.4	92.4
180	74.0	73.5	..	..	91.5	91.9
200	..	..	..	..	..	..
210	..	..	82.6	81.8	..	..

TABLE III

Sample A.

	I_t , $C_{\text{KNO}_3} = 2.50 \times 10^{-2} (M)$		I_t , $C_{\text{KNO}_3} = 2.22 \times 10^{-2} (M)$		I_t , $C_{\text{KNO}_3} = 2.00 \times 10^{-2} (M)$	
	Obs.	Calc. $b = 0.063$ $a = 0.088$	Obs.	Calc. $a = 2.38 \times 10^{-2}$ $b = 1.68 \times 10^{-2}$	Obs.	Calc. $a = 0.0126$ $b = 0.0103$
0 min.	90.3	90.3	90.3	90.3	90.3	90.3
2	95.5	95.1	97.4	98.0	98.2	98.8
5	91.0	90.7	96.0	96.2	97.7	98.2
10	86.3	86.1	93.8	93.7	96.8	97.3
20	81.3	81.3	90.6	90.0	95.6	95.6
30	78.5	78.8	87.1	87.1	94.2	94.3
50	76.4	76.4	83.4	83.3	91.9	92.3
70	75.4	75.1	80.7	81.1	90.7	90.8
95	75.2	74.1	79.0	79.0	89.6	89.4
140	..	..	77.2	76.9	87.6	87.7

DISCUSSION

It will be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables I, II and III, that the observed values of Σn or I_t are in good agreement with those calculated from equation (2) or (3). In these experiments, electrolytes containing univalent counter-ions have been used the reason of which has been discussed later on. The values of α and β (or a and b) have been found from two suitable points on the curve drawn by plotting Σn (or I_t) against t .

FIG. 1.

In none of the two samples A and B of the ThO_2 sol, there is noticeable during coagulation any S-shape which has been reported by Desai and co-workers^{7,11}. The addition of

small quantities of Th^{4+} ions, however, causes the appearance of prominent S-shape besides lowering the velocity of coagulation. Keeping the coagulant ion-concentration the same, the higher the Th^{4+} ion concentration, the more prominent is the S-shape (vide Fig. 1) and this can be explained as follows:

When a positively charged ThO_2 sol is in equilibrium with an appreciable quantity of co-ions, e.g., Th^{4+} ions, in solution, no further adsorption of the co-ions takes place as a result of repulsion owing to the potential of the electrical double layer. If an electrolyte is now added to the system, this equilibrium is disturbed, the electrolyte tends to lower the double layer potential while the stabilizing ions by fresh adsorption tends to maintain it at its original value. The net effect will be a gradual lowering of the potential until it is stabilised at a lower level depending on the concentration of the added electrolyte and that of the stabilising ions present in the system. During the period the potential is falling, the rate of coagulation will increase and after the attainment of the new equilibrium potential, the coagulation will proceed at a steady rate for sometime. At this stage, however, with the increase in radius of the particles owing to aggregation, the repulsion energy between the particles will increase and cause the rate of coagulation to decrease. Thus there will be three stages in the process of slow coagulation, viz., (1) the first stage where the rate of coagulation increases showing the so-called autocatalytic nature, the second stage where coagulation proceeds at a steady rate corresponding to the new steady double layer potential, at a lower level, and (3) the final stage when the rate of coagulation falls due to increasing energy of repulsion. These phenomena will be quite marked when the stabilising ion is present in appreciable amount such as in sols dialysed for a short period used by Desai⁷ and Desai and co-workers¹¹. In well-dialysed sols, however, the concentration of the stabilising ions will be very low and on addition of electrolyte, the new equilibrium position will be attained in a short time and the autocatalytic nature will not be noticeable.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Tables II and III that the rate of coagulation of ThO_2 sol with KNO_3 is higher than that with KCl . With very low electrolyte concentration, almost linear transmission-time curve is obtained.

Since the coagulating concentration of the counter ion varies inversely as the sixth power of valency,¹² polyvalent ions, even when added in small amount, produce a turbidity immediately. The larger flocculi thus formed tend to settle down so that spectrophotometric investigation becomes unsuitable. This peculiarity first reported by Desai⁷ has also been observed by the present authors.

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